

Studies in the Cyclo-octane Series. Part-IX. Friedel-Crafts Reaction of the Anhydride of 1-Carboxycyclo-octane-1-acetic Acid with some Aromatic Substrates and Synthesis of 2,3-Benzo/substituted-benzospiro[5,7]tridecanes

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Manuscript received 4 May 1982, revised 30 June 1989, accepted 11 August 1989

The Friedel-Crafts condensation of the anhydride of 1-carboxycyclooctane-1-acetic acid with a number of aromatic substrates gave the keto acids (1a-i) which, except 1f and 1i, on catalytic reduction yielded the respective reduced acids. These on cyclisation with PPA followed by Clemmensen reduction furnished the title hydrocarbons.

SAHARIA and Tyagi¹ could not accomplish the preparation of the spiro systems (4) because reduction of the keto acids (1) by Clemmensen/W.K. method yielded only the neutral product and no reduced acids (2), the latter being the intermediates for getting the spiro systems, were obtained. These reduced acids have now been obtained by catalytic reduction of the corresponding keto acids.

Aiming at the preparation of 2, the preparations of 1a-d, 1f and 1g have been repeated and extended to the preparations of 1e, 1h and 1i. Structures of the keto acids have been confirmed by the hypobromite oxidation to the known acids, and ir (doublet at 1720-1670 cm⁻¹ corresponding to two C=O groups), uv and nmr spectral data.

All the keto acids, except 1f and 1i, owing to their insufficient amounts, have now been successfully reduced catalytically using Pd/C (10%) in a paar apparatus at 35-40 psi and 35-40° to get the reduced acids (2a-g). Lower frequency absorption due to the keto group disappeared in the ir spectra of these acids. 2a-g have further been cyclised with PPA to yield the cyclic ketones (3a-g) and reduced subsequently by Clemmensen method to give the spiro-hydrocarbons (4a-g).

The analytical data of the compounds agree with the calculated values within the limits of experimental error.

Experimental

1-Carboxycyclo-octane-1-acetic acid and the keto-acids (1a-i) were prepared following the reported method¹.

1-Carboxycyclo-octane-1-acetic acid: m.p. 154-55° (benzene) (lit. 154-55°); δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 1-2.0 (14H, bm, ring protons), 2.7 (2H, d, CH₂COOH); 1a (R₁=R₂=R₃=R₄=H), m.p. 152° (lit. 152°); λ_{max} (EtOH) 240 nm (243†); δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 1-2.0 (14H, bm, ring protons), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 7.4 (3H, m, ArH), 7.8 (2H, m, ArH); 1b (R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=CH₃), m.p. 136° (lit. 137°); λ_{max} (EtOH) 255 nm (256†); δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 1-2.0 (14H, bm, ring protons), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 7.2 (2H, d, ArH) and 7.8 (2H, d, ArH); 1c (R₁=R₂=H, R₃=R₄=CH₃), m.p. 141° (lit. 142°); δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 1-2.0 (14H, bm, ring protons), 2.3 (6H, s, ArCH₃), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂CO) and 7.1-7.6 (3H, m, ArH); 1d (R₂=R₄=H, R₁=R₃=CH₃) m.p. 140° (lit. 140°); λ_{max} (EtOH) 250 nm (251†), ϵ_{max} 9750; δ (CDCl₃) 1-2.0 (14H, bm, ring protons), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 7-7.5 (3H, m, ArH) and 12.0 (1H, s, COOH); 1e (R₂=R₃=H, R₁=R₄=CH₃) (benzene-petroleum ether) (b.p. 60-80°) m.p. 142° (Found: C, 75.4; H, 8.6. C₁₉H₂₆O₃ requires: C, 75.5; H, 8.6%); δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 1-2.0 (13H, bm, ring protons), 2.3 (6H, s, ArCH₃), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂CO) and 7.1-7.3 (3H, m, ArH); S-Benzylisothiuronium salt (dilute alcohol), m.p. 131°; 1f (R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=OCH₃), m.p. 147° (lit. 147°); λ_{max} (EtOH) 270 nm (276†), ϵ_{max} 12260; δ (CDCl₃) 1-2.0 (14H, bm, ring protons), 3.2 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.8 (2H, d, ArH), 7.8 (2H, d, ArH) and 11.2 (1H, s, COOH); 1g (R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=Cl), b.p. 120°/1 mm (lit. 114°/10⁻¹ mm); 1h (R₁=R₄=H, R₂R₃=

† Value corresponds to that of the parent acetophenone.

-(CH₂)₄-) (benzene), m.p. 142° (Found: C, 76.8; H, 8.5. C₂₁H₂₈O₈ requires: C, 76.8; H, 8.6%); 2,4-DNP(EtOH), m.p. 165-66°; λ_{max}(EtOH) 260 nm; ε_{max} 12 720; δ(CDCl₃) 1-2.0 (18H, m, 14-cyclo-octane ring protons+4H in β-CH₂ groups tetralin ring), 2.8 (4H, us, ArCH₂), 3.4 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 7.2-8.6 (3H, m, ArH) and 11.0 (1H, s, COOH); 1i (R₃=R₄=H, R₁R₂=-CH₂=CH₂-CH₂=CH₂-) (benzene), m.p. 126-27° (Found: C, 77.6; H, 7.5. C₂₁H₂₄O₈ requires: C, 77.8; H, 7.4%); 2,4-DNP (EtOH), m.p. 108°; δ(CDCl₃+TFA) 1-2.0. (14H, bm, ring protons), 3.4 (2H, s, CH₂CO) and 7.3-8.3 (7H, m, ArH).

1-[β-(Phenyl/Substituted-phenyl)ethyl]cyclo-octane-1-carboxylic acid (2a-g): The keto-acid (1; 0.0125 mol) in alcohol (25 ml) containing Pd/C (200 mg; 10%) was reduced by passing H₂ at 35-40 psi and 35-40° for 25-30 h. The alcoholic solution was then poured into water (250 ml) and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and ether removed to yield the reduced acid (65-70%).

2,3-Benz/Substituted-benz-1-oxospiro[5.7]tridecane (3a-g): The reduced acid (2; 0.0085 mol) was cyclised by heating with PPA (15 g P₂O₅ in 10 ml H₃PO₄) at 180-90° for 2 h to yield the spiro-ketone (55-65%).

2,3-Benz/Substituted-benzspiro[5.7]tridecane (4a-g): The spiro-ketone (3; 0.005 mol) was refluxed with Zn/Hg (20 g) and concentrated HCl (60 ml) for 65 h - fresh quantities of concentrated HCl (6 ml) being added every 6 h. The reaction product on working up in the usual manner gave the spiro hydrocarbon (45-55%).

The physical and spectral data of compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Substituent	M.p. °C/ (B.p. °C/mm)	2,4-DNP M.p. °C
2a	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	160	—
2b	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₃ =OH ^a	145	—
2c	R ₁ =R ₄ =H, R ₂ =R ₃ =OH ^a	192-93	—
2d	R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₁ =R ₃ =OH ^a	194	—
2e	R ₂ =R ₃ =H, R ₁ =R ₄ =OH ^a	150	—
2f	R ₁ =R ₄ =H, R ₂ R ₃ =(CH ₃) ₂ ^d	150-51	—
2g	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₃ =Cl	(185/10 ⁻¹)	—
3a	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H ^b	(160-62/10 ⁻¹)	117
3b	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₃ =CH ₃	(165/10 ⁻¹)	187
3c	R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₁ =R ₃ =CH ₃	(152-54/10 ⁻²)	155-56
3d	R ₁ =R ₂ =H, R ₃ =R ₄ =CH ₃ ^c	(125-27/0.5)	115
3e	R ₂ =R ₃ =H, R ₁ =R ₄ =CH ₃	(140-42/9)	145-46
3f	R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₁ R ₃ =(CH ₃) ₂ ^d	(185-86/10 ⁻²)	190
3g	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₃ =Cl	(110-12/0.5)	192
4a	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	(200/6)	—
4b	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₃ =OH ^a	(190-92/10 ⁻²)	—
4c	R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₁ =R ₃ =OH ^a	(180-81/1)	—
4d	R ₁ =R ₂ =H, R ₃ =R ₄ =OH ^a	(165-67/1)	—
4e	R ₂ =R ₃ =H, R ₁ =R ₄ =OH ^a	(151-52/9)	—
4f	R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₁ R ₃ =(CH ₃) ₂ ^d	82-3	—
4g	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₄ =H, R ₃ =Cl	(186-87/2)	—

^a δ(CDCl₃) 1-2.0 (16H, m, 14 cyclo-octane ring protons and OH, β to Ar ring), 2.2 (5H, m, ArOH, and ArOH₂), 7.0 (4H, s, ArH) and 11.4 δ (1H, s, COOH).

λ_{max}: ^b245, ^c255, ^d255 nm; these values are in fair agreement with that for the parent tetralones².

References

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